

Sustainable rehabilitation of quarries in Milos island: enhancement of indigenous plant community re-installation through integration of novel, microbiome-based restoration technologies.

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Introduction: Quarrying leaves behind degraded soils with characteristics that inhibit plant establishment and hinder ecological restoration. These limitations are further intensified by the strong seasonal climatic variations of the Mediterranean basin. Reintroducing native plant species is a promising strategy, as they possess traits shaped by long-term natural selection that support their establishment and persistence in local conditions. However, the dynamics of soil functions and properties during restoration remain elusive, especially whether restoration initiated from quarry deposits can ultimately lead to a state comparable to that of the natural ecosystem. Recent advancements in soil-plant system research emphasize the symbiotic relationship between plants and soil microbial communities, which are essential for plant growth and survival. This has led to the development of microbiome-based restoration technologies, which utilize plant-growth-promoting microorganisms to enhance soil recovery, restore plant biodiversity, and improve ecosystem stability. By harnessing the potential of native plant species and their microbiomes, these technologies offer a sustainable pathway for ecological restoration, particularly in post-quarrying landscapes. Future research should focus on optimizing these microbiome-based approaches and exploring their broader applications in restoring disturbed ecosystems, ultimately fostering resilience and ecological stability in arid and degraded environments.

Materials and Methods: This study conducted in three steps. Firstly, we monitored the evolution of soil properties and functions across a restoration chrono-sequence. We examined rhizospheric soil from three native phryganic species—*Calicotome villosa*, *Anthyllis hermanniae*, and *Sarcopoterium spinosum*—growing in new (>15 years) and old (>30 years) restoration sites, undisturbed natural areas and bare quarry deposits in Milos Island, Greece. We assessed soil organic carbon, nutrient availability, and enzymatic activities related to carbon, nitrogen, sulfur, and phosphorus cycling to evaluate the influence of restoration age on soil properties and functions. Following, we isolated microorganisms that live in close association with these plant species in their undisturbed natural areas and we construct single species and synthetic communities (SynComs) microbial inocula. These inocula applied in *Medicago arborea* plants grown in pots and we aim to identify the best combination of microbial strains that would lead to the best results in terms of growth and fitness, but also to the highest levels of tolerance to salinity stress. Finally, we investigated the effects of inoculation with the whole rhizospheric microbial communities (crude inocula) on the early plant growth and on the establishment of beneficial symbiosis with rhizobia and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) for the pioneer legume shrub *Anthyllis hermanniae*. After a six-month growth period half of the plants were destructively sampled and the other half were transplanted in the restoration field and harvested after two years. At harvest, the above and below ground biomass, nodulation, and the extend of AMF root colonization were measured.

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Results: Field monitoring results demonstrated a clear restoration gradient, with soil properties and functions improving significantly from quarry deposits to natural ecosystems. Natural sites consistently exhibited the highest soil organic matter (OM), mineral associated organic matter -C (MAOM-C) and -N (MAOM-N) and nutrient values revealing that quarry restoration promotes the carbon sequestration. that within each restoration stage, both season and plant taxon significantly influenced soil properties, with their effects increasing from the new restoration to the natural site.

A) PCA plot with the clusters of restoration gradient, from bare quarry deposits to new (>15 years) and old (>30 years) restoration sites up to undisturbed natural areas. **B)** Distribution of mineral associated organic matter -C (MAOM-C) across restoration gradient, from bare quarry deposits (pink) to new (>15 years) (blue) and old (>30 years) (orange) restoration sites up to undisturbed natural areas (green) **C)** Plant biomass of *Medicago arborea* across different inoculations.

Experimentation on different microbial inocula as a tool to enhance *Medicago arborea* growth and fitness demonstrated that synthetic community (SynCom) microbial inocula were more effective than single species under normal and stressed conditions. *Anthyllis hermanniae* plants that inoculated with its indigenous rhizospheric microbial community increased in biomass, both belowground and aboveground and favored in symbiotic associations, leading to increased nodulation, higher N₂ fixation rate and increased root colonization by AMF. After two years growing in the field, inoculated plants demonstrate enhanced growth characteristics and rhizosphere functions compared to non-inoculated.

Conclusions: In conclusion, inoculation of plants with the whole rhizospheric microbial community they maintain under natural conditions reinforces plant growth and performance in infertile and semi-sterile environments as barren quarry deposits, a strategy that may prove to be important for revegetation and restoration of soil functions.

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